

Analysis of Resonance and Linear Stability of Oblate Infinitesimal in the Neighborhood of Triangular Equilibrium Points for Triaxial Primaries in the Elliptic Restricted Three Body Problem

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Abstract—The present paper analyses the linear stability and resonance of oblate infinitesimal in the neighborhood of triangular equilibrium points of the system. In *ER3BP*, the system comprises of triaxiality of both the primaries. The range of values of μ and e for the linear stability of triangular equilibrium points has been found in presence of resonance and the existence of third order resonances has been shown graphically. The linear stability are satisfied and the system is stable in the resonance case $3\lambda_2 = 1$ and $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 0$ whereas the system is unstable for the resonance case $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$ and $\lambda_1 - 2\lambda_2 = 2$.

Keywords—Triaxial, Oblateness, Hamiltonian, Elliptic Restricted Three Body Problem.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the frame work of Elliptic Restricted Three Body Problem (*ER3BP*) the present paper is proposed to analysis of the linear stability and resonance of oblate infinitesimal when both the primaries are triaxial and are moving around the triangular equilibrium points. The *ER3BP* is widely studied as it is generalization of classical Restricted Three Body Problem (*R3BP*). The system consists of two finite bodies (known as Primaries) moving about the third body of infinitesimal mass is influenced by both the primaries and their common center of mass having no influence on each other. In elliptical orbit, the primaries are assumed to be moving.

Resonance can enhance their gravitational interaction and have both stabilizing and destabilizing effects. When the periods of two orbiting bodies (e.g. Jupiter and Saturn around the Sun) are in a ratio of small whole numbers $\left(\frac{T_s}{T_j} \approx \frac{5}{2}\right)$ is the simplest example of an orbital resonance occurs. For instant the Moon Gyanymeda, Europa and I_o are in a stable 1:2:4 orbital resonance around Jupiter.

The Kirk-wood gaps in the asteroid belt are probably due to the destabilization resonances with the Jupiter. Resonance among the natural frequencies of the system (e.g. Keplerian orbits of a pair of moon of a planet) often leads to difficulties in naive estimates of the effect of the perturbation (say of the moon on each other). The Trojan asteroids liberate (oscillate) around the 1:1 orbital resonance (i.e., the orbital period of Jupiter is in the 1:1 ratio with the orbital period of the Trojan asteroids) the asteroids Thule liberates around the 4:3 orbital resonance and several asteroids in the Hilda group liberate around the 3:2 orbital resonance.

There are several such stable orbital resonances among the satellites of the major planets and one involving Pluto and the planet Neptune. The analysis based on the restricted three body problem cannot be used for the satellite resonances, however except for the 4:3 resonance between Saturn's satellite Titan and Hyperion, Since the participants in the satellite resonances usually have comparable masses.

In the neighborhood of the triangular equilibrium pointsthe present study aims to investigate the condition of linear stability of oblate infinitesimal, when both the primaries are triaxial in the *ER3BP*. Under the range of linear stabilityit has been shown that resonances of the third order exist. By studying the linear stability in the presence of resonance the work is different from other works followed by the method proposed by Kumar [8].

For restricted/elliptic restricted three body problem the resonance/ non resonance cases of libration points was analyzed and studied by many authors Beauge [1], Chandra [2], Ferraz [4], Hadjidemetriou [5], Henrard [6,7], Kumar [8], Manju [9], Narayan [12,13], Subbarao [14], Thakur [16], and many others.

The present paper consists of six sections: Section I consists of introduction; Section II consists the equation of motion; Section III focuses on the first order stability of the Hamiltonian; Section IV consists of normalization of the Hamiltonian function H_2 and Section V consists of the study of resonance case. The discussion and conclusion are drawn in Section VI.

II. EQUATION OF MOTION

In the elliptic restricted three body problem the equation of motion of the infinitesimal mass is under oblateness and triaxial primaries in the pulsating, barycentric, and non-dimensional coordinates are given by the differential equations derived in Duggad et.al [3]and given in the following equation. In principle the notations follow the book of Szebehely [15]. The notation being done for adapting to the present problem, with some minor modifications presented as:

$$\begin{aligned}x'' - 2y' &= \frac{1}{1+e\cos\nu} \frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial x}, \\y'' + 2x' &= \frac{1}{1+e\cos\nu} \frac{\partial\Omega}{\partial y},\end{aligned}\quad (2.1)$$

where (') denotes differentiation with respect to ν , and

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega &= \frac{x^2 + y^2}{2} + \frac{1}{n^2} \left\{ \frac{(1-\mu)}{r_1} + \frac{\mu}{r_2} + \frac{(1-\mu)[(2\sigma_1 - \sigma_2) + A_4]}{2r_1^3} - \frac{3(1-\mu)[(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)y^2 + A_4]}{2r_1^5} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{\mu[(2\sigma_1' - \sigma_2') + A_4]}{2r_2^3} - \frac{3\mu[(\sigma_1' - \sigma_2')y^2 + A_4]}{2r_2^5} \right\},\end{aligned}\quad (2.2)$$

$$\text{where} \quad n^2 = 1 + \frac{3}{2}e^2 + \frac{3}{2}(2\sigma_1 - \sigma_2) + \frac{3}{2}(2\sigma_1' - \sigma_2'),$$

and

$$r_1^2 = (x + \mu)^2 + y^2; \quad r_2^2 = (x - 1 + \mu)^2 + y^2. \quad (2.3)$$

Here σ_1 and σ_2 are triaxiality parameters, σ_1 ($i=1,2$); the bigger and smaller primaries positioned at $(x_i, 0)$, $i=1,2$ have masses m_1 and m_2 .

III. FIRST ORDER STABILITY OF THE HAMILTONIAN

The dynamical system described by the equations of motion the perturbed Hamiltonian is given by the system (2.1) is presented as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}H &= \frac{1}{2}(P_x^2 + P_y^2) + (yp_x - xp_y) + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{e\cos\nu}{1+e\cos\nu} \right) (x^2 + y^2) - \frac{1}{(1+e\cos\nu)} \\ &\quad \left[\frac{1}{n^2} \left\{ \frac{1-\mu}{r_1} + \frac{\mu}{r_2} + \frac{(1-\mu)[(2\sigma_1 - \sigma_2) + A_4]}{2r_1^3} - \frac{3(1-\mu)[(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)y^2 + A_4]}{2r_1^5} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \frac{\mu[(2\sigma_1' - \sigma_2') + A_4]}{2r_2^3} - \frac{3\mu[(\sigma_1' - \sigma_2')y^2 + A_4]}{2r_2^5} \right\} \right].\end{aligned}\quad (3.1)$$

The generalized components of momentum are P_x and P_y . The two triangular equilibrium solutions are symmetrical to each other when the nature of motion near the two points will be the same. Hence, calculating the motion near the equilibrium point L_4 .

By the change of variables, shifting the origin to L_4 are given by

$$x = \xi + q_1; \quad y = \eta + q_2; \quad P_x = P_\xi + P_1; \quad P_y = P_\eta + P_2. \quad (3.2)$$

The point L_4 is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\xi &= \frac{1}{2} - \mu - \frac{e^2}{2(1-\mu)} - \frac{\mu e^2}{2(1-\mu)} + \frac{e^2}{2} - \left(\frac{11}{8} + \frac{1-3\mu}{2\mu} \right) \sigma_1 + \left(\frac{11}{8} + \frac{1-2\mu}{2\mu} \right) \sigma_2 + \\ &\quad \left(\frac{11}{8} - \frac{1}{1-\mu} + \frac{5\mu}{2(1-\mu)} \right) \sigma_1' + \frac{1}{2} \left(-\frac{7}{4} + \frac{1}{1-\mu} - \frac{3\mu}{(1-\mu)} \right) \sigma_2' + \left(2 - \frac{2}{1-\mu} + \frac{5\mu}{2(1-\mu)} \right) A_4, \\ \eta &= \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \left[1 - \frac{e^2}{3(1-\mu)} + \frac{\mu e^2}{3(1-\mu)} - \frac{e^2}{3} - \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{11}{8} - \frac{1-3\mu}{2\mu} \right) \sigma_1 + \frac{2}{3} \left(\frac{11}{8} - \frac{1-2\mu}{2\mu} \right) \sigma_2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \frac{2}{3} \left(-\frac{11}{8} + \frac{1}{1-\mu} - \frac{5\mu}{2(1-\mu)} \right) \sigma_1' + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{7}{4} + \frac{1}{1-\mu} - \frac{3\mu}{(1-\mu)} \right) \sigma_2' - \frac{2}{3} \left(2 + \frac{2}{1-\mu} - \frac{5\mu}{2(1-\mu)} \right) A_4, \right.\end{aligned}$$

$$P_\xi = -\eta, \quad P_\eta = \xi. \quad (3.3)$$

In the new variables the solutions of the equation (3.3) are given by the equilibrium position $q_1 = q_2 = P_1 = P_2 = 0$. In the powers of P_i and $q_i, i = 1, 2$ now, expanding the Hamiltonian function (3.1), we obtain

$$H = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} H_k = H_0 + H_1 + H_2 + H_3 + H_4 + \dots, \quad (3.4)$$

where, H_0 is a constant and H_1 is equal to zero. To analyze the linear stability considering only the value of H_2 , we have

$$H_2 = \frac{1}{2}(P_1^2 + P_2^2) + (p_1 q_2 - q_1 p_2) + \left(\frac{e \cos \nu}{1 + e \cos \nu} \right) (q_1^2 + q_2^2) + \frac{1}{2(1 + e \cos \nu)} [A q_1^2 - B q_1 q_2 - C q_2^2], \quad (3.5)$$

which can be rewritten as

$$H_2 = H_2^{(0)} + H_2^{(1)}, \quad (3.6)$$

where

$$H_2^{(0)} = \frac{1}{2}(P_1^2 + P_2^2) + (p_1 q_2 - q_1 p_2) + \frac{1}{2} [A q_1^2 - B q_1 q_2 - C q_2^2],$$

$$H_2^{(1)} = \left(\frac{e \cos \nu}{1 + e \cos \nu} \right) [(1 - A) q_1^2 - B q_1 q_2 + (1 + C) q_2^2], \quad (3.7)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} A &= \frac{1}{8} + \frac{19}{32} \left(\frac{e^2}{1 - \mu} \right) - \frac{19}{32} \left(\frac{\mu e^2}{1 - \mu} \right) - \frac{29}{32} e^2 + \frac{21}{16} \mu e^2 + \left(\frac{107}{128} + \frac{23}{32\mu} - \frac{171}{32} \mu \right) \sigma_1 + \\ &\left(-\frac{247}{128} - \frac{23}{32\mu} + \frac{177}{32} \mu \right) \sigma_2 + \left(-\frac{301}{128} + \frac{171}{32} \mu \right) \sigma_1' + \left(\frac{185}{128} - \frac{135}{32} \mu \right) \sigma_2' + \left(-\frac{1}{4} - \frac{41}{16} \mu \right) A_4, \\ B &= \sqrt{3} \left[\frac{3}{4} + \frac{31}{52} \left(\frac{e^2}{1 - \mu} \right) - \frac{2091}{1872} \left(\frac{\mu e^2}{1 - \mu} \right) - \frac{91}{104} e^2 - \frac{2431}{624} \mu e^2 + \frac{3}{2} \mu + \left(\frac{1187}{192} - \frac{3}{16\mu} + \frac{1063}{96} \mu \right) \sigma_1 + \right. \\ &\left. \left(-\frac{1759}{192} + \frac{13}{48\mu} - \frac{821}{96} \mu \right) \sigma_2 + \left(-\frac{289}{192} + \frac{4159}{192} \mu \right) \sigma_1' + \left(\frac{125}{192} - \frac{3923}{192} \mu \right) \sigma_2' + \left(\frac{37}{3} + \frac{973}{24} \mu \right) A_4 \right], \\ C &= \frac{5}{8} + \frac{73}{72} \left(\frac{e^2}{1 - \mu} \right) - \frac{323}{288} \left(\frac{\mu e^2}{1 - \mu} \right) - \frac{241}{144} e^2 + \frac{563}{288} \mu e^2 + \left(-\frac{1401}{128} + \frac{27}{32\mu} + \frac{2215}{512} \mu \right) \sigma_1 + \left(\frac{1305}{128} - \frac{27}{32\mu} - \frac{2743}{512} \mu \right) \sigma_2 \\ &+ \left(-\frac{537}{128} - \frac{1104}{512} \mu \right) \sigma_1' + \left(\frac{309}{128} + \frac{201}{32} \mu \right) \sigma_2' + \left(-\frac{585}{32} + \frac{297}{32} \mu \right) A_4. \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

IV. NORMALIZATION OF THE HAMILTONIAN FUNCTION H_2

In *ER3BP* adopting the method given by Markeev [10] stability of the triangular points shall be studied. Subsequently we first normalize the Hamiltonian upto second order given by (3.6). The canonical transformation is considered for normalization

$$[q_1, q_2, p_1, p_2] = [q_1', q_2', p_1', p_2'] N, \quad (4.1)$$

where,

$$N = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 & a_1 c_1 & -a_1 c_1 & a_1 (1 - \omega_1 b_1) \\ a_2 & a_2 c_2 & -a_2 c_2 & a_2 (1 - \omega_2 b_2) \\ 0 & a_1 b_1 & a_1 (1 - b_1) & a_1 c_1 \\ 0 & -a_2 b_2 & a_2 (1 - b_2) & -a_2 c_2 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.2)$$

and,

$$a_i = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{2l_i}{\left| \omega_i^2 - \frac{1}{2} \right|}}; \quad b_i = \frac{2}{l_i}; \quad c_i = -\frac{B}{l_i}. \quad (4.3)$$

Assuming the frequencies ω_2 and ω_1 given by the relations $\omega_2^2 = -\{\lambda_{3,4}^{(0)}\}^2$ and $\omega_1^2 = -\{\lambda_{1,2}^{(0)}\}^2$, we obtain

$$\omega_{1,2}^2 = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left\{ 1 - \frac{4951}{256} \mu \sigma_1 + \frac{4159}{256} \mu \sigma_2 - \frac{379}{16} \mu A_4 + \frac{309}{32} \mu \sigma_1 - 21 \mu \sigma_2 \right\} \pm \left\{ \left(1 - \frac{4951}{128} \mu \sigma_1 + \frac{4159}{128} \mu \sigma_2 - \frac{379}{8} \mu A_4 + \frac{309}{16} \mu \sigma_1 - 42 \mu \sigma_2 \right) - 27 \mu (1 - \mu) \left(1 + \frac{1063}{72} \sigma_1 - \frac{821}{72} \sigma_2 + \frac{973}{18} A_4 - \frac{1967}{96} \sigma_1 - \frac{329}{32} \sigma_2 \right) \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] = 0. \tag{4.4}$$

The transformation (4.2) reduces the Hamiltonian (3.6) to the form

$$H_2' = \frac{1}{2} \left(p_1'^2 + \omega_1^2 q_1'^2 \right) - \frac{1}{2} \left(p_2'^2 + \omega_2^2 q_2'^2 \right) + \frac{e \cos \nu}{1 + e \cos \nu} \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} a_{\nu\mu}' q_1^{\nu_1} q_2^{\nu_2} p_1^{\mu_1} p_2^{\mu_2}, \tag{4.5}$$

where, $\nu = (\nu_1, \nu_2)$, $\mu = (\mu_1, \mu_2)$ such that $\nu + \mu = \nu_1 + \nu_2 + \mu_1 + \mu_2 = 2$.

The coefficients $a_{\nu\mu}'$ are given as

$$\begin{aligned} a_{2000}' &= \left[(1 - A) a_1^2 + B a_1^2 c_1 + (1 + C) a_1^2 c_1^2 \right], \\ a_{0200}' &= \left[(1 - A) a_2^2 + B a_2^2 c_2 + (1 + C) a_2^2 c_2^2 \right], \\ a_{0020}' &= \left[(1 + C) a_1^2 b_1^2 \right], \\ a_{0002}' &= \left[(1 + C) a_2^2 b_2^2 \right], \\ a_{1100}' &= \left[2(1 - A) a_1 a_2 + B a_1 a_2 c_1 + B a_1 a_2 c_2 + 2(1 + C) a_1 a_2 c_1 c_2 \right], \\ a_{1010}' &= \left[B a_1^2 b_1 + 2(1 + C) a_1^2 b_1 c_1 \right], \\ a_{1001}' &= \left[-B a_1 a_2 b_2 - 2(1 + C) a_1 a_2 b_2 c_1 \right], \\ a_{0110}' &= \left[B a_1 a_2 b_1 + 2(1 + C) a_1 a_2 b_1 c_2 \right], \\ a_{0011}' &= \left[-2(1 + C) a_1 a_2 b_1 b_2 \right], \\ a_{0101}' &= \left[-B a_2^2 b_2 - 2(1 + C) a_2^2 b_2 c_2 \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{4.6}$$

Now, using the transformation

$$q_i = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega_i}} \tilde{q}_i, \quad p_i = \sqrt{\omega_i} \tilde{p}_i, \tag{4.7}$$

The Hamiltonian gets transformed as

$$\tilde{H}_2 = \frac{1}{2} \omega_1 (\tilde{p}_1^2 + \tilde{q}_1^2) - \frac{1}{2} \omega_2 (\tilde{p}_2^2 + \tilde{q}_2^2) + \frac{e \cos \nu}{1 + e \cos \nu} \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} \tilde{a}_{\nu\mu} \tilde{q}_1^{\nu_1} \tilde{q}_2^{\nu_2} \tilde{p}_1^{\mu_1} \tilde{p}_2^{\mu_2}, \tag{4.8}$$

where, $\tilde{a}_{\nu\mu}$ is given as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{a}_{2000} &= \omega_1 a_{2000}', & \tilde{a}_{0200} &= \omega_2 a_{0200}', \\ \tilde{a}_{0020} &= \frac{1}{\omega_1} a_{0020}', & \tilde{a}_{0002} &= \frac{1}{\omega_2} a_{0002}', \\ \tilde{a}_{1100} &= \sqrt{\omega_1 \omega_2} a_{1100}', & \tilde{a}_{1010} &= a_{1010}', \\ \tilde{a}_{1001} &= \sqrt{\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_2}} a_{1001}', & \tilde{a}_{0110} &= \sqrt{\frac{\omega_2}{\omega_1}} a_{0110}', \\ \tilde{a}_{0011} &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{\omega_1 \omega_2}} a_{0011}', & \tilde{a}_{0101} &= a_{0101}'. \end{aligned} \tag{4.9}$$

Introducing the complex conjugate variable given by

$$q_j'' = \tilde{p}_j + i \tilde{q}_j; \quad p_j'' = \tilde{p}_j - i \tilde{q}_j; \quad j = 1, 2. \tag{4.10}$$

The Hamiltonian given by (4.8) is reduced to the form, $H_2'' = 2i \tilde{H}_2$, where

$$H_2'' = i \omega_1 q_1'' p_1'' + i \omega_2 q_2'' p_2'' + 2i \frac{e \cos \nu}{1 + e \cos \nu} \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} a_{\nu\mu}'' q_1^{\nu_1} q_2^{\nu_2} p_1^{\mu_1} p_2^{\mu_2}. \tag{4.11}$$

The coefficients in H_2'' are such that $a_{\nu\mu}'' = \bar{a}_{\nu\mu}'$,

$$a_{2000}'' = \frac{1}{4} \left\{ -\tilde{a}_{2000} + \tilde{a}_{0020} - i \tilde{a}_{1010} \right\},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 a''_{0200} &= \frac{1}{4} \{-\tilde{a}_{0200} + \tilde{a}_{0002} - i\tilde{a}_{0101}\}, \\
 a''_{1100} &= \frac{1}{4} \{-\tilde{a}_{1100} + \tilde{a}_{0011} - i\tilde{a}_{1001} - i\tilde{a}_{0110}\}, \\
 a''_{1001} &= \frac{1}{4} \{-\tilde{a}_{1100} + \tilde{a}_{0011} - i\tilde{a}_{1001} - i\tilde{a}_{0110}\}, \\
 a''_{1010} &= \frac{1}{2} \{\tilde{a}_{2000} + \tilde{a}_{0020}\}, \\
 a''_{0101} &= \frac{1}{2} \{\tilde{a}_{0200} + \tilde{a}_{0002}\}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.12}$$

Next, in complex conjugate variables to reduce the Hamiltonian (4.11) to normal form, the following transformation is applied

$$(q'', p'') \rightarrow (q_j^{**}, p_j^{**}),
 \tag{4.13}$$

which is defined by the generating function

$$q_1'' p_1^{**} + p_2'' q_2^{**} + S(q_1'', q_2'', p_1^{**}, p_2^{**}, \nu) \text{ where } S = \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} s_{\nu\mu} q_1^{\nu1} q_2^{\nu2} p_1^{*\mu1} p_2^{*\mu2}.
 \tag{4.14}$$

$S_{\nu\mu}$ are to be chosen 2π periodic function of ν . The relation between the variables is given as

$$q_j^{**} = q_j'' + \frac{\partial S}{\partial p_j^{**}}, \quad p_j'' = p_j^{**} + \frac{\partial S}{\partial q_j''}.
 \tag{4.15}$$

From the above relation, we have

$$H_2^{**} \left(q_j'' + \frac{\partial S}{\partial p_j^{**}}, p_j^{**}, \nu \right) - H_2'' \left(q_j'', p_j^{**} + \frac{\partial S}{\partial q_j''}, \nu \right) = \frac{\partial S}{\partial \nu}.
 \tag{4.16}$$

Now equating the coefficients of same powers on both sides, expanding the Hamiltonian by using Taylor's theorem, we derive

$$\begin{aligned}
 & i\lambda_1 q_1'' p_1^{**} + i\lambda_2 q_2'' p_2^{**} + i \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} (\mu_1 \lambda_1 + \mu_2 \lambda_2) s_{\nu\mu} q_1^{\nu1} q_2^{\nu2} p_1^{*\mu1} p_2^{*\mu2} - i\omega_1 q_1'' p_1^{**} - i\omega_2 q_2'' p_2^{**} - \\
 & 2i \frac{e \cos \nu}{1 + e \cos \nu} \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} a''_{\nu\mu} q_1^{\nu1} q_2^{\nu2} p_1^{*\mu1} p_2^{*\mu2} - i \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} (\nu_1 \omega_1 - \nu_2 \omega_2) s_{\nu\mu} q_1^{\nu1} q_2^{\nu2} p_1^{*\mu1} p_2^{*\mu2} = \\
 & \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} \frac{ds_{\nu\mu}}{d\nu} q_1^{\nu1} q_2^{\nu2} p_1^{*\mu1} p_2^{*\mu2}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.17}$$

Taking the terms up to second order in e

$$\begin{aligned}
 & i\lambda_1 q_1'' p_1^{**} + i\lambda_2 q_2'' p_2^{**} + i \sum (\mu_1 \lambda_1 + \mu_2 \lambda_2) (e s^{(1)} + e^2 s^{(2)}) - i\omega_1 q_1'' p_1^{**} - i\omega_2 q_2'' p_2^{**} - \\
 & 2i \left[e \cos \nu - \frac{e^2}{2} (1 + \cos 2\nu) \right] \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} a''_{\nu\mu} q_1^{\nu1} q_2^{\nu2} p_1^{*\mu1} p_2^{*\mu2} - i \sum_{\nu+\mu=2} (\nu_1 \omega_1 - \nu_2 \omega_2) (e s^{(1)} + e^2 s^{(2)}) = \\
 & \left(e \frac{ds^{(1)}}{d\nu} + e^2 \frac{ds^{(2)}}{d\nu} \right),
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.18}$$

where,

$$s_{\nu\mu} = e \sum s^{(1)} + e^2 \sum s^{(2)},
 \tag{4.19}$$

and taking

$$\lambda_i = \lambda_i^{(0)} + e \lambda_i^{(1)} + e^2 \lambda_i^{(2)} + \dots, \quad i = 1, 2.
 \tag{4.20}$$

Now, equating the coefficient of same powers of e on both sides of equation (4.18), we have

$$\lambda_1^{(0)} = \omega_1; \lambda_2^{(0)} = \omega_2; s_{\nu\mu}^{(1)} = \frac{2i a''_{\nu\mu} [\sin \nu + i \{(\nu_1 - \mu_1) \omega_1 - (\nu_2 - \mu_2) \omega_2\} \cos \nu]}{[(\nu_1 - \mu_1) \omega_1 - (\nu_2 - \mu_2) \omega_2]^2 - 1}.
 \tag{4.21}$$

By virtue of periodicity of $s_{1010}^{(1)}$ and $s_{0101}^{(1)}$, we have $\lambda_1^{(1)} = \lambda_2^{(1)} = 0$. The complex-valued generating function S correct

up to $O[e]$ so, equation (4.21) completely determines. Finally, reducing the Hamiltonian, $\tilde{H}_2 = \tilde{H}_2^{(0)} + \tilde{H}_2^{(1)}$ to the normal form, we obtain

$$H_2^* = \frac{1}{2} \lambda_1 (q_1^{*2} + p_1^{*2}) + \frac{1}{2} \lambda_2 (q_2^{*2} + p_2^{*2}). \tag{4.22}$$

By means of generating function the transformation is given by $\tilde{q}_1 p_1^* + \tilde{q}_2 p_2^* + K(\tilde{q}_j, p_j^*, \nu)$, where K is restricted to $O[e]$, and the relation between the variables is given by

$$q_j^* = \tilde{q}_j + \frac{\partial K}{\partial p_j^*}, \quad \tilde{p}_j = p_j^* + \frac{\partial K}{\partial q_j^*}. \tag{4.23}$$

The relation between the complex canonical variables with the real ones taking into the account given by equation (4.10)

$$q_j^{**} = p_j^* + i q_j^*, \quad p_j^{**} = p_j^* - i q_j^*.$$

From the equation (4.15), S is taken to the order of e and is given by $S^{(1)} = W$, we have

$$\tilde{q}_j = q_j^* - \frac{1}{2i} \frac{\partial W}{\partial p_j^*}, \quad \tilde{p}_j = p_j^* + \frac{1}{2i} \frac{\partial W}{\partial q_j^*}. \tag{4.24}$$

From, equation (4.22) and (4.24), we get

$$K = \frac{1}{2i} W, \tag{4.25}$$

where the function $K = \sum K_{\nu\mu} q_1^{*\nu1} q_2^{*\nu2} p_1^{*\mu1} p_2^{*\mu2}$ is real valued function. The coefficient is given by using the relation (4.7) and (4.21) as

$$\begin{aligned} k_{2000} &= \frac{1}{2i} (-s_{2000}^{(1)} - s_{0020}^{(1)} + s_{1010}^{(1)}), & k_{0200} &= \frac{1}{2i} (-s_{0200}^{(1)} - s_{0002}^{(1)} + s_{0101}^{(1)}), \\ k_{0020} &= \frac{1}{2i} (s_{2000}^{(1)} - s_{0020}^{(1)} + s_{1010}^{(1)}), & k_{0002} &= \frac{1}{2i} (s_{0200}^{(1)} - s_{0002}^{(1)} + s_{0101}^{(1)}), \\ k_{1100} &= \frac{1}{2i} (s_{1100}^{(1)} + s_{1001}^{(1)} + s_{0110}^{(1)} - s_{0011}^{(1)}), & k_{1010} &= (s_{2000}^{(1)} - s_{0020}^{(1)}), \\ k_{1001} &= \frac{1}{2} (s_{1100}^{(1)} + s_{1001}^{(1)} - s_{0110}^{(1)} - s_{0011}^{(1)}), & k_{1001} &= \frac{1}{2} (s_{1100}^{(1)} + s_{1001}^{(1)} - s_{0110}^{(1)} - s_{0011}^{(1)}), \\ k_{0101} &= (s_{0200}^{(1)} - s_{0002}^{(1)}), & k_{0110} &= \frac{1}{2} (s_{1100}^{(1)} + s_{1001}^{(1)} + s_{0110}^{(1)} - s_{0011}^{(1)}), \\ k_{0011} &= \frac{1}{2i} (s_{1100}^{(1)} + s_{1001}^{(1)} + s_{0110}^{(1)} + s_{0011}^{(1)}). \end{aligned} \tag{4.26}$$

By equation (4.22), the Hamiltonian H_2 has been transformed to normal form given correct up to first order in eccentricity e . This is obtained using equation (4.2), (4.7) and (4.23) and by equation (4.26) the corresponding coefficient of the generating function K .

V. RESONANCE CASES

We have to examine the presence of resonances for the study of stability. By applying the *KAM* theorem and taking third order terms and considering the value of λ_1 and λ_2 up to second order of e . As the value of $\lambda_1^{(1)} = \lambda_2^{(1)} = 0$, so the quantities $\lambda_1^{(2)}$ and $\lambda_2^{(2)}$ are found by the periodicity conditions of the function $s_{1010}^{(2)}$ and $s_{0101}^{(2)}$. Using (4.18) and equating the terms of e^2 , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{ds_{1010}^{(2)}}{d\nu} &= -2i \cos \nu (4a_{0020}'' s_{2000}^{(1)} + a_{1010}'' s_{1010}^{(1)} + a_{1001}'' s_{1001}^{(1)} + a_{0110}'' s_{1100}^{(1)}) + 2i \cos^2 \nu a_{1010}'' + i \lambda_1^{(2)}, \\ \frac{ds_{0101}^{(2)}}{d\nu} &= -2i \cos \nu (4a_{0002}'' s_{0200}^{(1)} + a_{0110}'' s_{1001}^{(1)} + a_{0101}'' s_{0101}^{(1)} + a_{0011}'' s_{1100}^{(1)}) + 2i \cos^2 \nu a_{0101}'' + i \lambda_2^{(2)}. \end{aligned} \tag{5.1}$$

Using equation (4.21) and the condition of periodicity of $s_{1010}^{(2)}$ and $s_{0101}^{(2)}$, the values of $\lambda_1^{(2)}$ and $\lambda_2^{(2)}$ are computed as

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_1^{(2)} &= -\frac{\omega_1\omega_2^2(6\omega_1^2-7)}{4(4\omega_1^2-1)(2\omega_1^2-1)}, \\ \lambda_2^{(2)} &= -\frac{\omega_1^2\omega_2(6\omega_2^2-7)}{4(4\omega_2^2-1)(2\omega_2^2-1)}.\end{aligned}\quad (5.2)$$

The value of N giving the resonance be

$$k_1\lambda_1 + k_2\lambda_2 = N. \quad (5.3)$$

The value of μ correct up to order of e^2 is given as: $\mu = \mu^{(0)} + e^2\mu^{(2)}$. For small value of e , where $\mu^{(2)}$ is the value of μ for $e \neq 0$ and $\mu^{(0)}$ is the value of μ for $e = 0$ taken up to order of e^2 , following Narayan et al. [13].

Taking, $\lambda_i = \lambda_i(\mu^{(0)} + e^2\mu^{(2)})$, $i = 1, 2$ and expanding by Taylor's theorem

$$\lambda_i = \left(\lambda_i^{(0)} + e^2\lambda_i^{(2)}\right) + e^2\mu^{(2)}\left(\frac{d\lambda_i}{d\mu}\right)_0, \quad i = 1, 2, \quad (5.4)$$

where $\lambda_1^{(2)}, \lambda_2^{(2)}$ are given by equation by (5.2). Now putting the above obtained values in equation (5.2) and equating the coefficient of e^2 to zero, we obtain

$$\mu^{(2)} = \frac{k_1\lambda_1^{(2)} + k_2\lambda_2^{(2)}}{k_2\frac{d\omega_2}{d\mu} - k_1\frac{d\omega_1}{d\mu}}. \quad (5.5)$$

Substituting different values of k_1, k_2, N in the above equation, the value of third order resonances are calculated and the value of $\mu^{(2)}$ is calculated on putting the value $\mu = \mu^{(0)}$.

Let us assume, the third order resonance occur for

- i. $3\lambda_2 = -1$,
 - ii. $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 0$,
 - iii. $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$,
 - iv. $\lambda_1 - 2\lambda_2 = 2$.
- (5.6)

The stability of the system can be examined by calculating the values of $\mu^{(2)}, \mu^{(0)}$ and $e = 0$ for different resonance cases and plotting the graphs between values of μ and ω . The graphs have been plotted using MATLAB software.

VI. CONCLUSION

The linear stability and resonance cases of the elliptic restricted three body problem with oblateness primary and triaxial secondary has been analyzed. It is observed from the graphs (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2) that the linear stability is satisfied for the resonance cases $3\lambda_2 = -1$ and $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 0$. On the other hand, the condition of linear stability does not hold for the resonance cases $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$ and $\lambda_1 - 2\lambda_2 = 2$ which are clear from the graphs in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. These results are in confirmation with Kumar [8].

Fig.1 Analysis of stability for $3\lambda_2 = -1$

Fig. 2 Analysis of stability $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 0$

Fig. 3 Analysis of stability for $2\lambda_1 + \lambda_2 = 1$

Fig. 4 Analysis of stability for $\lambda_1 - 2\lambda_2 = 2$

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